

Analytical Applications of 3-Anilino-2-Thiotetrahydroquinazole-4-One (ATQ-4-O) I-Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II)

A. K. SINGH* and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

and

N. K. RALHAN

Department of Chemistry, Panjabi University, Patiala

Manuscript received 2 January 1979, accepted 9 July 1980

3-Anilino-2-thiotetrahydroquinazole-4-one (ATQ-4-O) is synthesised and use of its Pd(II)-complex in the spectrophotometric determination of metal is explored. Pd(II)-ATQ-4-O complex absorbs maximum at 370 (ϵ 8400) and 380 nm (ϵ 10700) respectively in 60% acetone and chloroform media. Composition of the complex is 1 : 2 (metal : ATQ-4-O) in both the media. Accurate conditions for micro-determination of palladium in 60% acetone and by extractive procedure are developed. Study of diverse ion effect reveals that large quantities of other ions including platinum-metals (except osmium) either do not interfere or can be masked with suitable masking agents. Extractive procedure is more selective and sensitive. ATQ-4-O is more sensitive than pyrimidine-2-thiols.

SEVERAL heterocyclic thiols have been investigated for the spectrophotometric determination of the platinum-metals by Singh and co-workers¹⁻⁷. Among them 1-substituted pyrimidine-2-thiols are most promising reagents for the selective determination of palladium(II)¹⁻³. In continuation of these studies a new heterocyclic thiol 3-anilino-2-thiotetrahydroquinazole-4-one (ATQ-4-O) is synthesised and examined for analytical purpose. Of the platinum metals it reacts with palladium(II) and osmium(VIII) in cold (acidic medium) forming intense coloured complexes suitable for their spectrophotometric determination. Other platinum metals react with this ligand on prolonged heating. Due to this reason large amounts of all other platinum-metals except osmium are tolerable in the photometric determination of palladium. This is similar to what is observed with pyrimidine-2-thiols—a higher selectivity for palladium. In the present communication results of investigations on complexation of ATQ-4-O with palladium(II) carried out with a view to establish optimum conditions for determination of the metal spectrophotometrically are reported.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligand (ATQ-4-O) :

It involves two steps. In the first phase 6-aminobenzoyl- β -phenyl hydrazide is obtained from isatoic anhydride, which is converted into 6-anilino-2-thiotetrahydroquinazole-4-one by reaction with

carbon disulphide in the second step. Details of both reactions are as follows :

6-Aminobenzoyl- β -phenylhydrazide :

Isatoic anhydride (16.5 g ; 0.1 mole) and phenylhydrazine (10.8 g ; 0.1 mole) dissolved in ethanol (50 ml) were refluxed on a water bath. The evolution of carbon dioxide which started immediately, abated in about two hr. It was refluxed further for about 1 hr. Solvent was removed under vacuum and the compound thus precipitated was recrystallised from ethanol. The m.p. was 169-170° and yield 18.2 g (80%). Calculated C, 68.73% ; H, 5.72% ; N, 18.83% ; found C, 69.0% ; H, 5.64% ; N, 18.23%.

3-Anilino-2-thiotetrahydroquinazole-4-one :

Sodium hydroxide (2.4 g ; 0.06 mole) dissolved in water (10 ml) was added to a cooled solution of 6-aminobenzoyl- β -phenylhydrazide (11.35 g ; 0.05 mole) and CS₂ (7.6 g ; 0.1 mole) in ethanol (50 ml) in a 250 ml conical flask. The flask was stoppered and left overnight on a magnetic stirrer. The mixture was diluted with water (50 ml) and made acidic with acetic acid. The precipitated compound was filtered, washed with water and dried. After final recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid its m.p. was 236-238° and yield 12.0 g (90%). Calculated C, 62.44% ; H, 4.09% ; N, 15.61% ; Found C, 62.13% ; H, 4.15% ; N, 15.73%.

* Present Address : Department of Chemistry, M. D. University, Rohtak-124 001.

Preparation of solutions :

Standard solution of Pd(II) was prepared by dissolving anhydrous PdCl₂ (Johnson Mathey) in 1 M hydrochloric acid. It was standardised gravimetrically before use⁶. Ligand solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts in chloroform (0.005 M) and in acetone (0.01 M). All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Doubly distilled water was used throughout the work.

Apparatus :

UV and visible spectra of ligand and its palladium(II)-complex were recorded with Cφ-16 Russian spectrophotometer. IR spectrum in Nujol mulls of ligand was recorded on Perkin-Elmer 521 model IR spectrometer.

Procedure for determination in 60% acetone :

To a suitable aliquot containing 10-80 μg of palladium(II) add sufficient amount of concentrated HCl, so that in final solution acid concentration (in 10 ml) is in the range 2-4 M, and 3 ml of 0.01 M, ATQ-4-O solution in acetone. Make up the volume to 10 ml, keeping 60% acetone (V/V) in the medium and measure its absorbance, at 370 nm against reagent blank. Determine the metal content from calibration curve.

Extractive procedure :

Take a solution containing 20-70 μg of palladium in separating funnel. Add to it 2-6 ml of 10 M HCl and make up the volume to 10 ml. Shake this solution with 10 ml of 0.005 M ATQ-4-O in chloroform for about 15 min. Separate the organic phase and measure its absorbance at 380 nm against reagent blank. Calculate the palladium contents from precalibrated graph.

Results and Discussion

ATQ-4-O can exist in thiol(I) as well as in thione(II) form. However the IR spectrum of solid compound does not have band in 2500-2600 cm⁻¹ region. This indicates that ligand does not contain

free -SH group in the solid state although it may behave as thiol in solution. The presence of a sharp but very weak band at 2470 cm⁻¹ indicates that the proportion of hydrogen bonded thiol is also very small in solid state than the concentration of thione form. Occurrence of thioamide bands

I, II, III and IV⁹⁻¹¹ at 1530, 1295 (m), 960 (m) and 740 cm⁻¹ (m) respectively further supports the existence of thione form in solid state.

Complexation reaction with Pd(II) :

Addition of colourless solution (λ_{\max} 328 nm) of ATQ-4-O in acetone to palladium solution in presence of hydrochloric acid results in the formation of golden-yellow colour (stable for 24 hr). Ligand as well as its Pd(II) complex precipitates if acetone contents are lowered below 50%. Thus studies on palladium(II) complex have been made in 60% (V/V) acetone medium. Alternately on shaking the acidic palladium(II) solution with ligand solution in chloroform, the metal ion passes as golden-yellow complex into organic phase. Extraction into carbon tetrachloride, *n*-butanol and benzene is also possible but absorbance values have been found to be lower in these media. Chloroform is thus chosen for extraction. Complexation reaction in both media is investigated with a view to explore its applicability for palladium determination. Optimum conditions for determination are established and effect of diverse ions is investigated for both procedures. Results are described below :

Palladium(II)-ATQ-4-O complex system in 60% acetone medium :

Yellow coloured palladium-ATQ-4-O complex absorbs maximum at 370 nm ($\epsilon = 8400$ l mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) in the 60% acetone medium. Effect of acid concentration on complexation is studied. The absorbance is maximal and constant in 2.0-4.0 M hydrochloric acid. Other mineral acids can also be used in place of HCl. For full colour development at least 25-fold excess of ligand over metal is required. Further excess does not affect the absorbance. Beer's law is obeyed upto 12.5 ppm of palladium. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is 0.0125 μg/cm². From Ringbom plot optimum concentration range for determination has been found to be 1-8 ppm. The relative standard deviation is ±0.96%. Metal to ligand ratio in complex has been found to be 1 : 2 by Job's and logarithmic methods.

Palladium(II)-ATQ-4-O complex in chloroform :

The extracted Pd-ATQ-4-O complex in chloroform absorbs maximum at 380 nm. The extraction efficiency is 99.5% in the presence of 2-6M hydrochloric acid and 20-fold molar excess of ligand. Further excess of ligand does not affect the efficiency. Sulphuric, phosphoric, perchloric and nitric acids are also equally good for extraction purpose. Shaking for 10 min on electrical shaker is sufficient for complete extraction. Beer's law is obeyed upto 10 ppm of metal. Accurate concentration for determination is 2-7 ppm of palladium. The relative standard deviation is ±0.82%. The

values of molar extinction coefficient and Sandell's sensitivity are $10700 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.01 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ respectively. Composition of the complex in this medium has also been found to 1:2 (metal: ligand).

Effect of diverse ions :

Effect of diverse ions in the determination of 6 ppm of palladium is investigated. I^- , CN^- , SCN^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and thiourea interfere seriously in both media. Tolerance limits (with error of $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance) for other ions are incorporated in Table 1. Improvement in the tolerance limits for numerous cations is done with the use of suitable masking agent. Improved values are given in Table 2. Comparison of ATQ-4-O with pyrimidine-2-thiols¹⁻³ reveals that it is more sensitive and comparable in selectivity. However, the extractive procedure is more selective than the other one.

TABLE 1—TOLERANCE LIMITS FOR DIVERSE IONS

Foreign ion	Tolerance limit (ppm)	
	in 60% acetone medium	in extractive procedure
F^- or Br^-	2000	5000
NO_2^-	50	100
NO_3^-	5000	5000
CH_3COO^-	2000	5000
SO_4^{2-} ; SO_3^{2-}	5000; 1000	5000; 2000
$\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$	1500	3000
Tartrate	2000	3000
PO_4^{3-} ; BO_3^{3-}	5000; 2000	5000; 4000
Citrate	1000	3000
EDTA	1000	3000
Ca^{2+} or Sr^{2+} or Ba^{2+}	1000	3000
Zn^{2+} or Cd^{2+}	50	400
Sn^{2+} ; Hg^{2+}	40; 20	100; 50
Mn^{2+} ; Cu^{2+}	60; 5	1000; 25
Al^{3+} ; V^{5+}	80; 10	1000; 25
Ru^{2+} ; Rh^{2+}	40; 40	200; 200
Ir^{2+} ; Pt^{4+}	40; 20	200; 180
Ag^+ ; Au^{3+}	10; 10	50; 20
Os^{4+}	5	5
Fe^{3+} or Fe^{2+}	10	20
Co^{2+} ; Ni^{2+}	15	25

TABLE 2—IMPROVED TOLERANCE LIMITS FOR CATIONS IN PRESENCE OF MASKING AGENTS

Cations	Tolerance limits (ppm)		Masking agent
	in 60% acetone medium	in extractive procedure	
Cu^{2+}	25	500	EDTA or Citrate
Co^{2+}	50	700	EDTA
Ni^{2+}	50	600	EDTA or Citrate
Fe^{2+}	40	500	Fluoride
Al^{3+}	200	2000	Fluoride
Hg^{2+}	50	200	Citrate or Tartrate or EDTA
Sn^{2+}	100	250	Fluoride
Zn^{2+}	200	1000	Citrate or EDTA or Tartrate
Cd^{2+}	150	850	EDTA or Tartrate
Rh^{3+}	75	400	EDTA or Citrate

Further studies on analytical applications of ATQ-4-O are in progress and will be reported in subsequent parts of this series.

References

1. A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL, R. P. SINGH and N. K. RALHAN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 851.
2. A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL, A. M. BHATTI and N. K. RALHAN, *Talanta*, 1976, **23**, 937.
3. DEVLINA NATH, A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 467.
4. A. K. SINGH, R. P. SINGH and M. KATYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 650.
5. A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1978, **23**, 1153.
6. A. K. SINGH and R. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 428.
7. A. K. SINGH, M. KATYAL and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.* (in press).
8. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis (Longmans, London)", 1961.
9. C. N. R. RAO and R. VENKATA RAGHAVAN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 541.
10. C. N. R. RAO, R. VENKATA RAGHAVAN and T. R. KASTURI, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, **42**, 36.
11. I. SUZUKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1962, **35**, 1286, 1449, 1456.